

EXPERIENCE IN THE MANAGEMENT OF ARCHEOLOGICAL CULTURAL HERITAGE: POTENTIAL CONTRIBUTIONS TO UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article examines the management of archaeological cultural heritage and explores how international experience and best practices can contribute to the conservation and sustainable development of cultural heritage sites in Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *archaeological cultural heritage management, international experience, preservation and sustainable development of cultural heritage sites, Uzbekistan.*

Izoh. *Ushbu maqola arxeologik madaniy merosni boshqarishni o'rganadi va xalqaro tajriba va ilg'or tajribalar O'zbekistondagi madaniy meros ob'yektlarini saqlash va barqaror rivojlantirishga qanday hissa qo'shishi mumkinligini o'rganadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *arxeologik madaniy merosni boshqarish, xalqaro tajriba, madaniy meros ob'ektlarini saqlash va barqaror rivojlantirish, O'zbekiston.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается управление археологическим культурным наследием и исследуется, как международный опыт и передовые практики могут способствовать сохранению и устойчивому развитию объектов культурного наследия в Узбекистане.*

Ключевые слова: *управления археологическим культурным наследием, международный опыт, сохранение и устойчивое развитие объектов культурного наследия, Узбекистан.*

This presentation examines the management of archaeological cultural heritage and explores how international experiences and best practices may contribute to the preservation and sustainable development of heritage resources in Uzbekistan.

Archaeological cultural heritage encompasses a broad range of material remains consisting of archaeological sites, ancient monuments, cultural landscapes, surviving artifacts, and historical infrastructures. These constitute essential testimonies of past societies and collective identities.

The management of archaeological heritage is a complex and a context-dependent process shaped by legal frameworks, institutional structures, economic conditions, environmental factors, political priorities, and community engagement. Consequently, approaches to heritage management vary significantly between regions and countries according to their historical, cultural, political, social, and economic contexts.

This presentation focuses on the relationship between archaeological heritage and tourism. When appropriately managed, archaeological resources can contribute substantially to the development of sustainable tourism, regional economies, public education, and cultural diplomacy. Conversely, the pressure of increasing tourism can generate significant risks to the

preservation and integrity of archaeological sites, requiring attention to long-term planning and carefully balanced conservation strategies.

Drawing on selected international case studies and examples of good practices, this presentation highlights the importance of integrated conservation policies, interdisciplinary collaboration, digital documentation technologies, community engagement, and sustainable tourism management. These experiences provide valuable perspectives for Uzbekistan, a country possessing an exceptionally rich archaeological and historical heritage associated with the Silk Roads and the ancient civilizations of Central Asia.

Of course, the development of effective heritage management strategies in Uzbekistan is a process that should primarily be carried out by Uzbek specialists working in the fields of cultural heritage management, archaeological research, site conservation, and sustainable cultural tourism. To that end, it appears essential to strengthen, on the one hand, the international visibility of Uzbekistan’s exceptional archaeological heritage and, on the other hand, its potential for contribution to local and regional socio-economic development.

In this perspective, archaeological cultural heritage should not merely be taken as a scientific and historical resource. It should also be understood as a strategic component of sustainable development policies.